

gave a pale yellow compound, m.p. 140-1° (CHCl₃ : pet. ether); $\nu_{\text{Nujol}}^{\text{max}}$: 1710 cm⁻¹, 1660 cm⁻¹, 1610 cm⁻¹ and 1580 cm⁻¹. It gave an intense red colour with conc. H₂SO₄ and a dark blue-green spot on TLC (spray reagent 2% ceric sulphate in 2N H₂SO₄). These results indicate that the compound is probably a lignan. Further structural studies are still in progress.

n-Triacontanol: Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1) gave n-triacontanol⁶, m.p. 83-4° (EtOAc); C₃₀H₆₂O; IR, $\nu_{\text{Nujol}}^{\text{max}}$: 3110 cm⁻¹ (H-bonded O-H stretch), 1020 cm⁻¹ (C-O stretch), 730 and 720 cm⁻¹ [(—CH₂—)_n, n > 4, bending]; acetate (Ac₂O/pyr.) m.p. 66-7°.

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Chemical Constituents of the Roots of *Dichrostochys cinerea* Macb. and the Stembark and Heartwood of *Acacialeucophloea* Willd.

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DICHROSTOCHYS *cinerea* and *Acacia-leucophloea* both belong to the family Leguminosae. The roots of *D. cinerea* are astringent and used in rheumatism and renal troubles¹. The stembark, heartwood and leaves of *D. cinerea* have been examined earlier.² The flowers of *A. leucophloea* contain glucoside of myricetin³. This note reports the results of chemical examination of the roots of *D. cinerea* and stembark and heartwood of *A. leucophloea*.

Examination of the roots of *Dichrostachys cinera* Macb :

The coarsely powdered roots on benzene extraction yielded a semisolid mass which on chromatography over deactivated alumina yielded the following compounds :

n-Octacosanol: Elution of the column with petroleum-ether (60-80°) afforded crystalline n-octacosanol, m.p. 83-84°, acetate, m.p. 64-65°, identified (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic sample.

β-Amyrin: Further elution of the column with petroleum-ether (60-80°) furnished β-amyrin, m.p. 198-199°. It was identified on the basis of IR, m.m.p. and by preparing its acetate, m.p. 238°.

Friedelan 3-one: Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1) yielded friedelan-3-one, m.p. 260° and was confirmed by reduction (NaBH₄) to friedelan-3β-ol, C₃₀H₅₂O, m.p. 276-278° (m.m.p. TLC and IR.)

Friedelan-3β-ol: Further elution of the original column with petroleum-ether and benzene (9 : 1) afforded friedelan-3β-ol, m.p. 278°, identical (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic specimen. On acetylation it gave an acetate, m.p. 290-291°.

β-Sitosterol: Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) furnished β-sitosterol, m.p. 136-137°, acetate, m.p. 126-127°.

Examination of the Stembark of *A. leucophloea* Willd :

The benzene extract of the stembark on chromatography over deactivated alumina yielded the following compounds :

n-Hexacosanol: Elution with petroleum-ether (60-80°) afforded colourless n-hexacosanol, m.p. 79-80°, acetate, m.p. 64-65°.

β-Sitosterol: Further elution of the column with petroleum-ether-benzene (4 : 1) yielded β-sitosterol, m.p. 136-137°.

β-Amyrin: Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) afforded β-amyrin, m.p. 198° identical (mmp, TLC and IR) with an authentic specimen. On acetylation it gave an acetate, m.p. 238°.

Examination of the heartwood of *A. leucophloea* Willd :

The petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of the dried and coarsely powdered heartwood on chromatography over deactivated alumina yielded the follow-

ing compounds :

n-Octacosanol : Elution of the above column with petroleum ether yielded *n*-octacosanol, m.p. 83-84°, acetate, m.p. 65-66°.

β -*Sitosterol* : Further elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) gave β -sitosterol, m.p. 136°, acetate, m.p. 126°.

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Solvent Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Nickel(II) with Benzil- α -Monoxime

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A number of complexing agents have been used for the extraction and determination of nickel in different organic solvents^{1,2}. Among them oxime compounds are well known. In our laboratory benzil α -monoxime is under investigation to study the extraction behaviour of nickel. Previous use of the reagent has been reported by Paria³ and Ueda⁴ to extract platinum and cobalt. In the present communication a method is devised to extract and determine nickel spectrophotometrically in microgram levels with the reagent.

Experimental

Separating funnels (100ml) were used for the extraction purpose. Beckman DU2 Model Spectrophotometer with optically matched quartz cells (10mm path length) was used for optical density measurements.

Chloroform was distilled before use. Benzil- α -monoxime was prepared and purified in the laboratory⁵ in a good yield. A 1% acetonic solution of the oxime was used to extract nickel.

A stock solution of nickel(II) was prepared by dissolving 3.8 gm NiSO₄·7H₂O (E. Merck) in distilled water and diluted to 250ml. This was standardised gravimetrically with dimethylglyoxime⁶, contained 3.16 mg. Ni per ml. 125-fold dilution of this stock solution containing 25.3 μ g Ni per ml was used as the test solution for our routine work.

Buffer solution of different pH were prepared by standard procedures : Hydrochloric acid—potassium chloride (pH 1-2) ; acetic acid—sodium acetate (pH 3-6) , potassium hydrogen phosphate—sodium hydroxide (pH 9-11).

All other chemicals used were either chemically pure or reagent grade materials unless otherwise mentioned.

Recommended procedure for the determination of Ni(II)

An aliquot (2ml) of the test solution containing 50.6 μ g Ni was treated with 8ml buffer solution of desired pH in a separating funnel. To test the interference of the diverse ions the selected ions were added before. The volume of the aqueous phase was maintained at 10ml throughout the work. Benzil- α -monoxime in acetone (1ml, 1%) was added to the solution and kept for 10 min to ensure complete complexation. The aqueous phase was then shaken for 5 min with 10 ml chloroform. The layers were allowed to settle for 3 min and separated. The volume of the chloroform extract was made up to exactly 25 ml and the absorbance read at 360 and 400 nm against a reagent blank prepared under identical conditions. Nickel was determined accordingly from a previously prepared calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectrum

The absorption spectrum of Ni(II)-benzil- α -monoxime in chloroform shows that the chelate absorbs strongly below 310 nm and then the absorbance falls showing two absorption maxima at 360 and 400 nm. The reagent itself shows insignificant absorbances from 360 nm onwards. All the absorption measurements were carried out at 360 and 400 nm.

Effect of pH

The pH range 1-11 was studied in order to investigate the liquid-liquid extraction behaviour of the system. Extraction starts at pH 4 and becomes 100% at pH 9. In the pH range 7-10 extraction occurs to the extent of 95% or more. The extraction curve drops sharply beyond pH 10. The pH for 50% extraction are 6.3 and 10.9.

Calibration curve

Different amounts of nickel were taken and extracted as in the procedure at pH 9 and the corresponding absorbances measured in order to observe the adherence of the coloured system to Beer's law. In each case Ni was exhaustively extracted in 5 min ; the aqueous phases were always clear and colourless. The results show that Beer's law is closely obeyed at 400 nm over the concentration range of 15-90 μ g Ni per 25 ml of chloroform solution.